

DIET CHOICE EXPLAINS THE EMERGENCE OF ARCHITECTURE IN ANTAGONISTIC NETWORKS

Savannah Nuwagaba: savannah@sun.ac.za ,
 CIB, Dept. Mathematical Sciences, US
 Supervisors: C. Hui and F. Zhang

PROBLEM

Designing mechanistic model that can give rise to realistic architecture of ecological networks is central to the understanding of how species assemble and function in ecosystems. We here incorporate an interaction switch, as an adaptive behaviour of diet choice, into a bipartite network model, with the effect of antagonistic interactions between species depicted by Holling's type II functional response.

METHOD

The model

$$\frac{1}{P_i} \frac{dP_i}{dt} = r_i - e_i P_i - \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{a_{ij} v_{ij} H_j}{1 + h \sum_{k=1}^n a_{kj} v_{kj} P_k}$$

$$\frac{1}{H_j} \frac{dH_j}{dt} = -d_j + \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{b_{ji} a_{ij} v_{ij} P_i}{1 + h \sum_{k=1}^n a_{kj} v_{kj} P_k}$$

Description	GM	DNM	BNM
P Plant species' abundance	(0,1)	(0,1)	(0,1)
r Plant species' birth rate	(0,1)	1	(0,1)
e Plant species' death rate	(0,1)	1	(0,1)
H Herbivore's abundance	(0,1)	(0,1)	(0,1)
d Herbivore's death rate	(0,1)	1	(0,1)
a encounter possibility	{0,1}	{0,1}	{0,1}
v preference	(0,1)	(0,1)	0.5
b benefit	(0,0.2)	(0,0.2)	0.1
h handling time	0.1	0.1	0.1

GM: general; DNM: demography-neutral;
 BNM: benefit-neutral

Interaction switch algorithm

- randomly choose 2 herbivores
- one drops an interaction with a plant that contributes the least to its fitness
- the other randomly adds to its diet a plant that was not in its diet. (keep track of interaction matrices)

REFERENCES

- [1] Zhang, F., Hui, C. and Terblanche, J. S. 2011. An Interaction Switch Predicts the Nested Architecture of Mutualistic Networks. *Ecol. Lett.* 14: 797-803.
- [2] Nuwagaba, S., Zhang, F. and Hui, C. Diet Choice Explains the Emergence of Architecture in Antagonistic Networks. submitted.

RESULTS: FIG 1

The dynamics of modularity and nestedness in antagonistic networks. (A) and (B) show snapshots of interaction matrices. (C) and (D) illustrate the dynamics of the level of modularity and nestedness respectively predicted by the general, demography- and benefit-neutral models. Dashed lines indicate observed levels.

RESULTS: FIG 2

For 61 real networks, the figure shows predictions from the general model vs. observations ((A) and (D)), vs. initial random matrices ((B) and (E)), and vs. predictions from neutral models ((C) and (F))

RESULTS: FIG 3

For 61 real networks, (A) shows the relationship between modularity and nestedness; (B) shows the relationship between nestedness and connectance; (C) and (D) are examples of the predicted vs. observed node-degree distributions of one network. Open circles indicate predictions from the general model

RESULTS: TABLE 1

Summary of the model performance (t-statistic, P value and the slope from the RMA regression of row vs. column entries). The bottom left: modularity comparisons; the top right: nestedness (NODF). OBS: observations; GM: our general model; DNM: demographic neutral model; BNM: benefit-neutral model; RM: random matrices with the same connectance as the real networks.

	OBS	GM	DNM	BNM	RM
OBS		1.84	11.308	-0.23	12.891
		0.07	<0.001	0.819	<0.001
		1.07	1.473	1.049	1.504
GM	-1.099		16.705	-4.768	18.169
	0.276		<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
	0.97		1.377	0.981	1.047
DNM	3.599	17.347		-20.2024	10.399
	<0.001	<0.001		<0.001	<0.001
	0.923	0.952		0.712	1.021
BNM	-2.364	-3.167	-17.546		21.427
	0.021	0.002	<0.001		<0.001
	0.902	0.930	0.978		1.434
RM	4.985	19.053	4.304	17.05	
	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	
	0.97	1.001	1.051	1.076	

DISCUSSION

Evidently, our model not only predicts the architecture of antagonistic networks in terms of modularity, nestedness and species degree distribution, but also the relationship between modularity and nestedness and that between nestedness and connectance. This implies that the diet choice via an interaction switch plays a vital role in the structural emergence in ecological networks. In addition, we found that the demography-neutral scenario over-estimated observed modularity, whilst the benefit-neutral scenario over-estimate observed nestedness.

FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Using this model, one can investigate;

- the structural trajectory of an adaptive ecosystem.
- the diversity-complexity relationship
- the condition for species to diverge into distinctive functional modules
- robustness, resilience and invasibility